

Dynamical Pattern of Elementary Particles

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Abstract

This purpose of this present paper is to present the simple idea to introduce a mathematical model to predict some possible particles (and may be its systems) that might exist beyond standard model of particle physics. The idea that is discussed in this present note must somehow* be the particle does not belong to fermions or bosons but more exotic. This paper is purely theoretical which gives hypothetical flavor of particles that possibly claims to exist in nature, based on the weird but interesting mathematical sketch. This note has been done by keeping one sentences in mind that the existing particles can reveal the zoo of other unknown particles.

Keywords: Particle Matrices, quarks, component.

All the known (or may be some unknown particles) are originated from big bang so there must be a common factor to define its behavior and its birth via gigantic transformation** and in fact these known particles can reveal other of their friends***. In particle physics standard model plays a key role in explaining the obvious behavior of fundamental particles and interactions. The predictions from standard model are all confirmed including the quantum excitation of Higgs field (that generates mass due to electroweak gauge symmetry breaking). No more words let us move towards mathematical argument to form the fundamental basis of the present paper.

The mathematical requirement requires the introduction of mathematical idea here considered. The key idea is to define the mathematical setup notation as ψ_n which we would like to call as "Particle Matrices" it can be defined as proposed with four individual components.

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

If $\varphi_1\varphi_2\varphi_3\varphi_4$ are the four components of the particle matrices and φ_4 is the predicting component in the matrices, the necessary mathematical formulation can be defined as follows

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

Our massive limitation is the choice of four components to predict a particle in terms of weird but interesting mathematical model.

If we want to obtain the other particles from elementary fermions one must define such rules mentioned below by incorporating the fourth component φ_4

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

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The basic equation of the components (the pattern) can be given as

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/u + (\varphi_2 - \varphi_4) = 0$$

Where u is the unit to balance the equation based on choice (essentially for charge e and for spin is \hbar)

Consequently it follows

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/u = -(\varphi_2 - \varphi_4)$$

Such that it is mentioned earlier that

$$\psi_n = 0$$

Or the mathematical mechanism simply follows

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix} = \varphi_1\varphi_3/u + (\varphi_2 - \varphi_4) = 0$$

However there are several important rules which must be expressed.

Note:

1. No same particle's spin or charge cannot be repeated in choosing the components.
2. The above defined four parameters now will be charge and spin components of particles.
3. The charge and spin are taken here, of only particles that are discovered in nature.
4. The choice of spin and charge must be separate.
5. The particles can be described only by charge or only by spin based on independent choice. The resultant particle's charge and spin (if calculated) in this mathematical approach are taken as separate.

We will use fermions (only quarks) to predict the particles which may possibly exist in nature

For instance let us use boson

First consider the three components be the spin of bosons such that keeping the rules in mind first choice will therefore form

$$\varphi_1 = \text{spin of first gauge boson (photon)}$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{spin of second gauge boson (gluon)}$$

$\varphi_3 = \text{spin of third gauge boson (assuming only } w \text{ boson for weak interaction)}$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \varphi_4 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

From fundamental equation mentioned above we can predict the fourth component

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/\hbar + (\varphi_2 - \varphi_4) = 0$$

Such that the component φ_4 must have a **spin 2** and needs to be elementary (as we include vector bosons), which indeed preliminary a **spin 2 boson** which is not yet observed but many theories predict that graviton which is also a gauge boson of have spin 2. Simply means that our spin 2 boson must or must not be a graviton but indeed it's a spin 2 boson, if observed then our formulation of particle matrices is indeed correct. Spin 2 boson is beyond standard model of particle physics.

Taking charge of discovered baryons

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a Delta } ++ (+2)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a proton } (+1)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a positive sigma } (+1)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} +2 & +1 \\ \varphi_4 & +1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Component 4 thus becomes a particle of **charge +3** or any particle of charge (+++) integer. This simply means a particle of integer charge +3 may exist beyond the standard model of particle physics. Clearly it shows that baryons, mesons and tetraquarks (predicted below) must not possess charge +3 if and only if these particles are made with standard model six types of quarks. Any new type of particle might possess charge +3

However this particle may be composite or elementary. If composite then, we are not truly sure about its constitution.

Now for instance let us simply use the notation that meson which is a composite boson contains two quarks say $N=2$. Now simply use rule as follows

$$\varphi_1 = \text{meson } 1$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{meson } 2$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{meson } 3$$

Or setting

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 & m_2 \\ \varphi_4 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N_1 & N_2 \\ \varphi_4 & N_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Where N_1 is the number of quark and m_1 is the first meson contains in meson which is 2, so simply $N_1 = N_2 = N_3$

Using equation

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3 + (\varphi_2 - \varphi_4) = 0$$

We thus arrive that $\varphi_4 = 6$ which therefore must be a particle composed of six quarks simply hexaquark.

Using simple expressions one can deduce that if baryon (contains three quarks)B and meson (contains two quark) then

$$B + m = h$$

Where h is pentaquark. Here B and m are denoted by their number of quarks N

Simply if T is the tetraquark (contains 4 quarks)

$$T + m = H$$

Where H is the hexaquark.

Therefore from our simple mathematical patterns we predict that **tetraquark and hexaquark particle should and must exist.**

For quarks charge

Choice 1

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a up quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a down quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a charm quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} +2/3 & -1/3 \\ \varphi_4 & +2/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Component 4 thus becomes a particle of charge of +1/9

Choice 2 for charge

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a down quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a up quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a charm quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} -1/3 & +2/3 \\ \varphi_4 & +2/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Component 4 thus becomes a particle of charge of +4/9

Choice 3

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a up quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a down quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a bottom quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} +2/3 & -1/3 \\ \varphi_4 & -1/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Computing we get the component φ_4 is of charge -5/9, say $\theta = -\frac{5}{9}$

Choice 4

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a strange quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a down quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a bottom quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} -1/3 & -1/3 \\ \varphi_4 & -1/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get the component φ_4 is of charge -2/9, say $\emptyset = -\frac{2}{9}$

Choice 5

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a top quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a up quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a charm quark } (+2/3)$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} +2/3 & +2/3 \\ \varphi_4 & +2/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get the component φ_4 is of charge +10/9, say $\emptyset_p = +\frac{10}{9}$

Choice 6

$$\varphi_1 = \text{charge of a down quark } (-1/3)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \text{charge of a top quark } (+2/3)$$

$\varphi_3 = \text{charge of a strange quark } (-1/3)$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} -1/3 & +2/3 \\ \varphi_4 & -1/3 \end{pmatrix}$$

We get the component φ_4 is of charge $+7/9$, say $\varphi_q = +\frac{7}{9}$

Charges of newly predicted particles must be

$$A = +1/9, B = +4/9, \theta = -\frac{5}{9}, \varphi = -\frac{2}{9}, \varphi_q = +\frac{7}{9}, \varphi_p = +\frac{10}{9}$$

All others detailed analysis must be experimental.

These particles must have their own antiparticle given by equation based on charge choices

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/e + (\varphi_2 + \varphi_4) = 0$$

Simply

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 & \varphi_2 \\ \varphi_4 & \varphi_3 \end{pmatrix} = \varphi_1\varphi_3/e + (\varphi_2 + \varphi_4) = 0$$

Formula for calculating the charge of quarks

According to Mr. Murray Gell-Mann three flavors of quark exists (discovered six) up, down and strange for which the charge must be given by Gell-Mann Nishijima formula

Form 1 Gell-Mann Nishijima formula

$$Q = e \left[I_3 + \frac{1}{2}(B + S) \right]$$

However the above formula does not sufficiently satisfy other three quarks, therefore independently

We derived empirical relations for the charge of quarks only from its baryon number

Form 2 our equations

$$Q = L_3(B + 1) \text{ for quark of charge } + 2/3$$

Form 2 is true for up, charm quark and top quark $L_3 = +\frac{1}{2}$ is the weak isospin of left quarks (up, charm, top)

Form 3

$$Q' = -L_3(B - 1) \text{ for quark of charge } - 1/3$$

Form 3 is true for down, strange and bottom quark $L_3 = -\frac{1}{2}$ is the weak isospin of left quarks (down, strange, bottom)

Where I_3 the isospin spin of quark, S is the strangeness, and B is the baryon number.

However we have predicted the charge of other new particles above which we strongly believe to exist in nature.

Consequently for spin choice, since fermions have spin $\frac{1}{2}$ therefore

Setting spin choices we get

Since all quarks (fermions) of spin half therefore

$$\varphi_1 = 1/2$$

$$\varphi_2 = 1/2$$

$$\varphi_3 = 1/2$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1/2 & 1/2 \\ \varphi_4 & 1/2 \end{pmatrix}$$

From

$$\varphi_1\varphi_3/\hbar + (\varphi_2 + \varphi_4) = 0$$

We obtain φ_4 of spin $\frac{3}{4}$, therefore the new particle of spin $\frac{3}{4}$

Other choice (since spin of quarks can be $\pm\frac{1}{2}$)

$$\varphi_1 = 1/2$$

$$\varphi_2 = -1/2$$

$$\varphi_3 = 1/2$$

$$\psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1/2 & -1/2 \\ \varphi_4 & 1/2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We obtain φ_4 of spin $\frac{1}{4}$, therefore the new particle of spin $\frac{1}{4}$

So all possible spin choice will give spin $\pm\frac{1}{4}$ and $\pm\frac{3}{4}$

Other prediction: spin of all six new particles may be somehow based on the figures $\frac{3}{4}, -3/4, \frac{1}{4}, -1/4$ or any other particle may exist of above predicted spins. Therefore these particles must not be fermions or bosons but something super exotic and highly exciting.

This particle matrices works with bosons, leptons and hadrons (mesons and baryons)

However these particles above mentioned must needs to be experimentally confirmed in super high energy accelerators, these particles must decay in a very tiny fraction of a fraction of a second because it is very unstable and produce in extreme high energy collisions. All others properties must be determined experimentally. If any other theoretical explanations it will be present elsewhere.

The search for these particles through experiments at super high energies is highly suggested.

* The agreement will complete when we will observe these particles.

** The known particles are formed due to something unknown transformed during big bang.

*** The garden of other unknown particles.